

Outlier Detection in Physiological Data with Stalactite Demography Representation

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Abstract

In recent times, outlier detection has been used to detect points that are used to consider abnormal data attributes that don't fit in a particular pattern. In its highly practical nature, outlier detection is used in many real-world use cases. One of the most famous cases of the use of outlier detection is in financial fraud and malicious transactions for tracking abnormal relations by intelligence agencies using intelligent analytical tools. The outlier detection algorithms are very useful for any parastatals and can help to explore common outlier detection procedures and applications to big data environments. One of its major drawbacks is that it can be intimidating and look complex for an average person. This paper discusses a straight method of detecting outliers based on the categorization of data samples from a physiological study of users on e-learning and interactive webpages. There are two thousand datasets containing both synchronise physiological response and eye movement behaviour of users to dynamic contents and the major aim is to detect outlying cases due to errors in measurement and environmental factors. The dataset was categorised into data generated from the Adult response, Student response, Younger users' response and Children's response. The result shows there is an outlying case in children's response data than the others because kids are not much conversant with e-learning and hence their reaction is based on straightforward tasks and mixed visual representation of eye movement and behaviour patterns.

Keywords: Outlier detection, Intelligent analytical, Detection procedures, Categorised data patterns, Physiological response, Eye movement behaviour

Outlier Detection with Stalactite

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1 INTRODUCTION

In most companies that make use of a huge amount of data, outlier detection can help to identify suspected fraudulent cases and transactions for companies that use a credit card in daily transactions, it can

be used to identify abnormal brain signals that may be or indicated in the early stage to brain cancers. In most cases, anomaly or outlier detection is more likely checking the engine light of a car and gives an alert when there is a tweak, repairs, and also maintenance that needs to be looked after [1, 2, 3, 4, 5].

Daily, outlier detection is used to run businesses, even in the dark ages when they were at a disadvantage. There are also analytical tools like in technology stacks. Anomaly detection is usually the only way to identify unusual transactions and cases in a given situation. The analytical software for anomaly detection is created and hovers in the background of some companies to determine marketing, budget, security failures, and optimisation [6, 7, 8, 9, 10].

The company management teams are always alerted when an opportunity or risk arises to handle them in more strategic and logical procedures embedded in the application, most 61% of these executive parastatals use these AI analytical tools to identify problems and find opportunities and procedures they might have missed. One of the biggest advantages of these companies adopting outlier detection is taking care of the most task that matters to optimise their procedures and rules. The major disadvantage of outlier detection is that it intimidates data processing due to its complexity, especially in models like the neural network in artificial intelligence. Another problem is that the outlier is naturally different from other members of the dataset, this means that outlier detection techniques can detect potential outliers, but the final interpretation of the result is still based on human effort.

In big data environments, there is a significant difference between the older generation of big data analytics and outlier detection and the current times. The amount of data and velocity with which data is created needs extra dedicated time. Just like millions of social media posts message transactions and videos are created, outlier detection techniques need to possess the capability to process data almost in real-time. The models adopted need to showcase potential outliers immediately. Because the information that the outlier detection provides is time-sensitive e.g. credit card detection and malicious chatter are time-sensitive and need real-time attention [11, 12, 13, 14, 15].

Some research also claims that big data has changed the game of outlier detection, and big data has also opened up a world of opportunities to get more value from outlier detection techniques. Because the larger the dataset becomes, the more value outlier detection will bring. There is also an analogy that considers the famous task of finding a string of anomalies in a huge amount of web access data that gives outlier detection algorithms more value. And as the value of outlier detection keeps increasing with the size of data created, there will exist more use cases of outlier detection in big data. Some of these cases include fraud detection and card transaction, intrusion detection of unauthorised access to computer networks, activity monitoring by detecting malicious messages and other forms of web interactions and quality control detection of production defects. This is intended as an exhaustive list of a use case

of outlier detection and merely an illustration of how big data has significantly changed the spectrum for outlier detection [16, 17, 18, 19, 20]. The paper presents a novel way of outlier detection on user physiological response and eye movement generated data from an experimental setup with dynamic e-learning and cataloguing websites. The proceeding sections discuss the methods and results obtained for the study.

2 METHOD

An experimental setup was conducted that involved ninety participants, each participant signed a consent to take part in the experiment where users had to sit in front of an eye tracker and place their hands on a Skin Conductance Response (SCR) sensor where their physiological reading was taken while they interact with dynamic contents of e-learning and cataloging sites. Their cognitive response to the visual interface served as a stimulus and was classified as “*stress mood*” and “*relaxed mood*”, depending on the level of SCR in both tonic and phasic changes. The framework for data generation is indicated in Figure 1. Where the SCR parameter and eye movement parameters (pupil measure and baseline) are saved as a dataset and linked to an inference engine (dynamic motor control) that produces residuals for outlier detection.

The data generated for the study is simulated to two thousand, this is served as input to the inference engine which produces residuals for outlier detection. The aim is to see which outlying cases are detected and whether excluding them or including them in the data will increase the performance of models i.e. excluding outlier cases such as environmental factors will help optimise the process in user-generated data for specified model integration. A custom algorithm based on detecting standard structures in the dataset is used in the following model equation:

$$f(x) = \iint_{i=1}^N X_{i=1}^n \forall i \in X. \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} y &= [rep(X_1^{n-p}), rep(X_n X_{n-p})]. \\ x &= [rep(X_1^n), rep(X_{n-p})]. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where $X_{(i-1)}^n$ is the input matrix, y and x are the residual coordinates from the input matrix and n and p are the start and endpoint respectively for each outlier detected. This is based on the Mahal, the least square distance from the starting point. At first, all instances appear as outlying and then the most outlying case is detected with a starting point and follows this pattern till outlying cases are detected. This is a means of using the r interaction. Figure 2 shows a window frame of the pseudocode form of the algorithm in R language and implemented in R . The outliers allow us to determine which sites are most complex during interaction based

Figure 1: Framework for data generation and outlier detection.

on the outliers detected. The result is indicated in the result section of the paper.

3 RESULT

The *R* language is used for analysing and recording big data, and data such as that obtained from both a physiological response and eye movement on webpages consist of user attributes that could amount to a million instances per second, this data is used as the inference input. The initial state is to visualise and understand the nature of the data (i.e. determine whether they are of clustered series or spatial attributes) and then decide which form of inference engine to adopt. The structured residuals are still another way of determining the nature of the dataset. Based on Figure 3, the data is seen to be clustered and outliers are used to determine which of the instances is the best fit to be included in the model for pattern classification and recognition. The generated datasets consist of four groups of individuals, Adult response, Student response, Younger users' response, and Children's response.

The previous version of the model [2, 1] used the method (structured residuals) to understand natural structures in the dataset. The novel contribution to this method is being able to classify these residuals based on two response states (stress mood and relaxed). In this process, we can be able to know which instances are outlying and what cognitive response is related to such outlying cases. The nature of the class will determine whether it is best to replace the instance or exclude it from the set inference engine. The datasets for younger participants (Figure 3), show that stress reaction to the dynamic contents on webpages is less than the relaxed mood. This response signal signified a relaxed mood and is mostly found on the e-learning website (*www.zyro.com*). This shows that children would be more adaptive and comfortable using and getting their lectures or lessons online. The first outlying case started with a residual score of 0.7324 for an *R2* and was very feasible for behaviour response data.

The data generated for Adult responses (aged be-

```

codeR-with-plot - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
s <- 1:n
ind <- matrix(0, n-p, n)
ind1 <- 0
thresh <- qchisq((n-0.5)/n,p)
index<-1:(p+1)
for(i in (p+1):n) {
  ind1<-ind1+1
  if(i==(p+1)) D<-mahal(x,index)
  index<-order(D)
  index1<-sort(index[1:i])
  D<-mahal(x,index1)
  index2<-s[D>thresh]
  ind[ind1,index2]<-ind[ind1,index2]+1
}

y<-rep(1:(n-p),rep(n,(n-p)))
x<-rep(1:n,(n-p))
#labs =paste(row.names(xx))
datf = data.frame(URL = xx[1], x =x,y = y, Status = x)

#datf$URL <- factor(datf$URL, levels = datf$URL)
par(mai = par("mai") * c(1, 1, 2, 1))
residuals <- c(".")[as.vector(t(ind[(n-p):1])) + 1]
p = ggplot(data = datf, aes(x = URL, y, label = residuals))
ylab("Number of observations used for estimation") #+
p1 = p + theme(text = element_text(size=12), axis.text
legend.position = "none") + scale_y_reverse() + scale

```

Figure 2: Pseudo-form algorithm of outlier detection and finding natural patterns in the categorized data.

Figure 3: Outlier detection on Children group in response data to dynamic webpages.

Figure 4: Outlier detected for Adult group to interaction to dynamic contents.

tween 40 – 60) (Figure 4) shows that stress mood is the most detected instance from the user interaction and these are found on e-learning sites rather than the cataloguing sites. One major important knowledge is that Adults find it difficult to understand certain knowledge processes online due to webpage complexity. Some visual aesthetics usually render the page unapproachable

and difficult to navigate. E-learning sites should contain very few controls and important buttons that are related to what the site portrays. Visual aesthetics, though add a more approach visual to websites but should be portrayed to a minimal contest. The outliers detected have a starting point of 0.76 residual scores and are also very feasible for user behaviour-defined data. The residual

detected at the initial start serves as the performance for the data model in terms of outliers detected online. This way one can also test the reliability and consistency of the data model when compared to a receiver operating characteristics.

In Figure 5, the data generated for Student cognitive response to e-learning and dynamic cataloging webpages shows that stress mood is the most detected instance from the user interaction. Also, one major knowledge is that this group also finds it difficult to understand certain knowledge processes online due to webpage complexity. And some visual aesthetics usually renders the page withdrawn and difficult to navigate. The e-learning websites should contain very few controls and important buttons that are related to what the site portrays as detected from the above results. The visual aesthetics on these pages, though add a more approach visual to websites and should be portrayed as a minimal contest. The outlying detect has a starting point of 0.86 residual scores and is also very feasible for user behaviour-defined data. Subsequent residual score detected at the initial starting point serves as the performance for the data model in terms of outlier detected as compared to the other data models. These significant results show the dependability of mood detection using the outlier detection algorithm.

Figure 6 also shows that stress mood is the most detected class responsible for the user interaction data with a starting point of 0.87 residual score and perfect performance rate compared to the others (Children participants) the response state is found mostly found at the cataloging website where one can use it as an e-learning tool for purposing e-books and course materials, response rate depends mostly on the visibility of the dynamic contents and whether the user found it more approachable than the other websites.

4 CONCLUSION

This paper tries to investigate a systematic outlier detection in data categorization generated from physiological traits, the method proposes a straight method of detecting outliers based on the categorization of data samples from a physiological study of users on e-learning and interactive webpages. There are two thousand datasets containing both synchronise physiological response and eye movement behaviour of users to dynamic contents and the major aim is to detect outlying cases due to errors in measurement and environmental factors. The dataset was categorised into data generated from the Adult response, Student response, Younger users' response, and Children's response. The result shows there is an outlying case in children's response data than the others because kids are not much conversant with e-learning but can be adaptive to the new process hence their reaction is based on straightforward tasks and mixed visual representation of eye movement and behaviour

that produces more of the relaxed mood than the stress mood. Anomaly detection is aimed to be one of the widely used analytics tools that will be applied to most big data models especially those that involve data generated from online interactions to understand behaviour data.

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Figure 5: Outlier detection for Student cognitive response to dynamic webpages.

Figure 6: Outlier detection on Younger participants group in response to dynamic contents.

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